

FEATURES OF ECO-HUMANISM DEVELOPMENT IN YOUTH

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ABSTRACT: The foundation of society's civilization is education, which involves passing down the experience, knowledge, culture, and spirituality acquired by our ancestors to future generations. Therefore, the key to human survival on our planet, especially in today's harsh environmental conditions, is an education system that emphasizes the interaction between humans and nature. From a scientific standpoint, developing eco-humanism among all citizens, including students, is crucial in solving environmental problems and preventing them from arising in the future..

KEY WORDS : eco-humanism, student youth, social consciousness, environmental knowledge, environmental culture, environmental problems .

Modernity is defined by the aspiration to reconcile the relationship between humanity and nature. It is fair to say that philosophy in the twentieth century rejected the dichotomy between subject and object, human and nature that was prevalent in the New Age movement. Nature came to be seen as the abode in which humanity resides. The term 'ecology' stems from the Greek word 'oikos', which means 'home'. Thus, ecology is the study of the home. Alas, the development of ecology occurs under the constant accompaniment of environmental disasters threatening humans associated with environmental pollution, resource shortages, overpopulation, and the destruction of the "humanity-nature" system. Having managed to get into an environmental crisis, humanity does not know any clear ways out of it. Despite the implementation of programs to develop waste-free production and improve environmental legislation, the environmental crisis continues. It is becoming more and more obvious that the main environmental problem lies not in nature, but in the value and ethical ideas of man and society.

The unyielding principles of humanism must be linked not only with mankind, but also with nature. This is where humanism transitions to eco-humanism. Human love, which was selfishly directed solely towards oneself, has ultimately led to an ecological crisis. Eco-humanism, unlike traditional humanism, considers human existence as a part of nature. Therefore, we must treat nature as carefully as we treat ourselves. Nature is valuable to us, to current and future social systems.

As science and technology advanced in civilized countries, violence against humans reduced, however, human violence against nature increased. The exploitation of nature seems to have partly replaced the exploitation of humans. That is why humanism extended to the natural environment has become essential. A concept is needed that could respond to the challenge of the century, to all the current crises combined - environmental, social,

intrapersonal. Ecological humanism, the main idea of which is the renunciation of violence against nature and man, is intended to be such a response.

Modern civilization does not teach the ability to live together with people and nature. Aggressive consumer orientation, with its desire to take from nature everything that a person wants, has led to an environmental crisis. The current environmental situation gives impetus to a new type of civilization.

The traditional understanding of humanism, according to Heidegger, is metaphysical. But being can give itself, and a person can treat it with reverence, which brings the approaches of Heidegger and Schweitzer closer together. Nature enters the sphere of morality as a consequence of the increased scientific and technological power of man.

The trouble with Western civilization, according to Schweitzer, is that it tried to be satisfied with a culture divorced from ethics. But the ultimate goal should be the spiritual and moral perfection of the individual. New European culture believed that spirituality would come with increased material well-being, but this did not happen. Schweitzer wrote: "For a truly moral person, all life is sacred, even that which, from our human point of view, seems inferior." Following Tolstoy and Gandhi, who spoke about the law of love, Schweitzer writes about the will to love, which seeks to eliminate the very duality of the will to life. Heidegger revealed the insufficiency of Renaissance humanism in our time. Criticizing modern humanism, Heidegger essentially led to the need for a synthesis of the humanism of Confucius with new European humanism. This synthesis will not be a simple combination of one and the other, but a qualitatively new formation corresponding to our time. The synthesis of Western and Eastern humanism should combine the adherence to moral maxims with the creation of something new.

"Humanism" now means, if we decide to keep this word, only one thing: the essence of man is essential for the truth of being, but in such a way that everything does not simply come down to man as such." Humanism comes from "homo", in which there is not only "man", but also "earth" ("humus" as the most fertile layer of the earth). And man is "homo" from the earth, and not just "men" from the mind and "anthropos" in itself. These three words contain three concepts of man. In "men" and "anthropos" there is nothing of the earth and humanity. Humanism (by the origin of the word) is understood as earthly, ecological. And "ecology" is the "home" of a person, his existence in the broad sense of the word.

Berdyayev spoke about punishment for humanistic self-affirmation. It lies in the fact that man has opposed himself to everything around him, when he should unite with it.

Ecological and social crises require practical humanism, but at the same time they force humanity to rise to a new theoretical level.

The path to a truly global consciousness and world culture does not lie through the suppression of some cultures by others or the rational construction of some new systems, but through the unification of people and nations on the basis of universal moral wisdom.

New ecological thought must be combined with traditional humanism, which is based on non-violence. This gives ecological humanism, which is the humanism of Confucius, Socrates, Christ and the Renaissance, extended to nature, the sprouts of which are in the philosophy of Tolstoy, Gandhi and others. Ethics must enter into culture, nature must enter into ethics, and through ethics, culture in ecological humanism is united with nature.

Ecological humanism lies at the intersection of Eastern and Western traditions. The West can give a lot in scientific and technical terms to solve environmental problems, India - the spirit

of ahimsa (non-violence), Russia - traditional patience and the gift of self-sacrifice. The synthetic power of ecological humanism is also expressed in the synthesis of the cultural sectors that took part in its creation. This is art, religion, philosophy, politics, morality, science.

The ethic of ecological humanism is the ethic of ahimsa, spread throughout the world. Ecological humanism requires a change in attitude towards nature (protecting animals, protecting the environment from pollution, etc.), towards people (preserving cultural and individual diversity), towards the Universe. Ecological humanism combines attitudes towards humans and animals, overcoming the paradox that people can fight for animal rights and not pay attention to violence against people. The rights of animals and people are equally sacred in it.

Ecological humanism is based on the principle of harmony between man and nature and recognition of the equal value of all living things. "The attempt to establish generally valid value differences between living beings goes back to the desire to judge them depending on whether they seem to us to be closer to a person or further away, which, of course, is a subjective criterion. For who among us knows what significance another living being has in itself and in the world as a whole?

To free himself from the power of nature, man resorted to violence. Now he is free (or rather, he thinks so), and nature has been defeated, and further violence is dangerous. People are beginning to understand that violence against nature is turning against them. And humanity towards nature will be another argument in justifying the need to abandon violence in interpersonal relationships.

Why is it important to be humane from an environmental point of view? Preserving existing diversity preserves the world, and not only the material world, which is the more stable the more diverse it is, but also the human soul, as modern psychology in the person of Fromm confirms. Let's add to this the argument of karma, which in Christianity is interpreted as punishment for sins. By refusing violence, we save nature and our souls.

The rationale for nonviolence in relation to nature is similar to that given by Tolstoy in relation to people. We do not know the universal truth, therefore, until it is found, we should not use violence against people. In relation to nature, we can say: we do not know the absolute truth, therefore, until it is discovered, we should not use violence against nature.

The situation in the environmental field has its own specifics. Man must regulate the forces of nature, as N.F. Fedorov demanded, but with love, and not with violence, as he does now. The concept of love for nature, which opposes the desire to dominate it, remains important, despite the use of scientific terminology of "regulation", "optimization", etc.

The material progress of consumer civilization cannot but lead to a crisis, because material needs, as already emphasized, in principle can grow indefinitely, conflicting with the ability of the biosphere to satisfy them. Ecological humanism allows us to weaken the antagonism of this contradiction.[15]

Ecological humanism as a modern form of humanism combines the struggle for social justice and anti-war actions, the "green movement" and the movement for animal rights and mercy. Its principles:

1. Harmony of man and nature.
2. Equivalence of all living things.
3. Non-violence (ahimsa).

4. Self-restraint instead of consumerism.
5. Formation of a loving and creative personality.
6. The need for moral self-improvement.
7. Personal responsibility for peace.
8. "The golden rule of ecology."
9. Non-cooperation with the exploiting classes.
10. Preservation of the diversity of nature, people and culture.

All great preachers of ecological humanism are highly characterized by the desire not only to think, but also to act. In ecological humanism, we come to an awareness of existence not only theoretically, but also practically - in our behavior. Humanism breaks through the framework of spiritual culture and enters the vastness of existence.

The new attitude of man to nature also has an impact on environmental law, that is, the system of legal norms regulating the interaction between man and nature. Environmental law can be understood in two main senses. First of all, this is the right of people to a healthy natural environment; compensation for damage to specific people and the state by polluting enterprises: environmental transparency, i.e. complete information about the state of the natural environment, association in various environmental organizations; environmental rallies, meetings, demonstrations, pickets, etc. This is one side of environmental law, which is an environmental addition to basic individual rights, which has become necessary in connection with the expansion of the scale of human activity.

CONCLUSION

To overcome the environmental crisis, we need to learn how to interact with nature non-violently and abandon the desire to conquer it. Violence is a part of life, but we have the power to reduce it by not desiring it. For those who believe that our actions have no impact, we must act as if they do and strive to make a difference.

In practical terms, environmental humanism involves appropriate behavior and even nutrition, such as non-violence and vegetarianism.

In conclusion, we must emphasize that morality, ethics, and ecological consciousness all play a role in regulating man's relationship with nature. However, they cannot be extended to nature as a source of influence on man or to the relationships between natural objects.

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